

Disability and Employment:

The Virtual (Offsite) Office

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Version Fall 2020

Web Site: <http://zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles>

See Also Zeller, D. (2011). United States: Disabilities and Workforce Diversity

Link https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CrEKnMRLJf4QqVKN_n47nAxH5HxdzX1clq8-rM12hpI/edit?usp=sharing

Abstract

Basically, technology can provide the ability to work from wherever; thus, circumventing the need for transportation to and accessibility in a “fixed workspace” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 56). Moreover, the use of technology that allows for adaptive work environments, including virtual offices and modified equipment, will enable skilled “individuals with disabilities to be a greater asset than non-disabled individuals lacking requisite skills” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p.56). The purpose of this article is to review existing studies on people with disabilities in the workplace by the renowned team of Frank Gilbreth and Dr Lillian Gilbreth; then apply their research to the current virtual office environment. The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this article, is a global enterprise; hence, the information will include an international perspective.

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Introduction

Organizations “successful in integrating disabled individuals into the workforce” recognize the value of diversity in achieving organizational goals and in gaining a “competitive advantage” in a dynamic, global marketplace (Davis, 2005). That is, a diverse workgroup enhances the initiatives of the company in ways that a homogenous population can not. Those initiatives include the areas of niche marketing, customer service, product development marketability, and in generating creative suggestions for strategic goals, among others (Kurlander, 2004). Another point to consider is that “ninety-five percent of Americans look favorably on companies who employ people with disabilities and 87 percent prefer to patronize these businesses” (Himmelstein & Salzano, 2010) (Zeller, 2011). On the other hand, the corporate culture is a “significant factor facilitating employment of individuals with disabilities” (Davis, 2005) (Zeller, 2011).

The major regulatory statute in the United States, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), passed in 1990, “is a federal law and covers all private employers with 20 or more employees, state and local governments (including school districts), employment agencies, and labor organizations” (Allbusiness.com, n.d.) From a human resource viewpoint, per the ADA, “reasonable accommodation” also means “equal opportunity, not merely equal treatment” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 58). In essence, persons with disabilities are looking for jobs with stability and potential for advancement. In any case, up-to-date job descriptions can help to ascertain that all applicants, including persons with disabilities, have the “requisite skills, educational background, and experience to perform the essential functions” (Dessler, 2004, p. 130). Likewise, performance appraisal systems should be based on the merit of the work; thereby, recognizing skilled employees ready for “higher levels of responsibilities” (Southwest ADA Center, n.d.) (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 60) (Zeller, 2011)..

According to the latest reports, there has been a 115% increase in virtual workers over the last decade; thus, changing where and the way that people work (Vasel, 2017). The concept of physical placement continues to evolve on a global scale as the hybrid (combined virtual / traditional) transnational organizations include the use of telework centers, collaborative online projects, and rotating schedules. Conclusively, the use of technology that allows for adaptive work environments, such as virtual offices and modified equipment, will enable skilled “individuals with disabilities to be a greater asset than non-disabled individuals lacking requisite skills” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p.56).

The purpose of this article is to review existing studies, by the renowned team of Frank Gilbreth and Dr Lillian Gilbreth, on people with disabilities in the workplace; then apply their research to the current virtual office work environment. The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this article, is a global enterprise; hence, the information will include an international perspective.

Definition of Terms

Americans With Disabilities Act (ADA): In the United States, the major regulatory statute, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), passed in 1990, “is a federal law and covers all private employers with 20 or more employees, state and local governments (including school districts), employment agencies, and labor organizations” (Allbusiness.com, n.d.)

Disabled Employees: In 2002, the World Health Organization (WHO) defined disability “as a part of a continuum of health, and as a universal experience.” With this definition, the World Health Organization (WHO) considered that “every individual can experience a decrement in health that could require an accommodation, such as a flexible schedule, medical leave, or modified work” (WHO, 2002 as cited in Davis, 2005) (Zeller, 2011). That is to say that each one of us could at some point in our lives become disabled; yet still need to continue to work (Zeller, 2011).

Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’) Offices: For this study, Hybrid (Virtual Offsite / Traditional ‘Brick and Mortar’) Offices will refer to a combination of physical and virtual workspace and scheduling in a multinational organization; e.g. the transnational model.

Transnational Organizations: Based on Bartlett and Ghoshal’s models of globalization (1989), the transnational approach, selected for this research, invites the transfer of practices to, from and within the affiliates; parent organizations and subsidiaries are aware of their own role as well as the role of others. There is high pressure for integration and high pressure for differentiation; knowledge and innovation is developed and distributed within the entire organization. In the transnational model, the practice of knowledge sharing also recognizes the benefits gained from local responsiveness and adaptation (Bartlett & Ghoshal, 2009).

Purpose and Significance

The purpose of this article is to review existing studies, by the renowned team of Frank Gilbreth and Dr Lillian Gilbreth, on people with disabilities in the workplace; then apply their research to the current virtual office environment. The transnational model of multinational organizations, selected for this article, is a global enterprise; hence, the information will include an international perspective.

Statistics sustain the significance of disability and employment issues. For example, according to the United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Disability report on global data, 80% to 90% of persons with disabilities of working age are unemployed; and between 50% and 70% in industrialized nations are unemployed (United Nations, n.d.). In the United States, in 2019, the Department of Labor, Bureau of Labor Statistics reported that “19.3 percent of persons with a disability were employed. In contrast, the employment-population ratio for persons without a disability was 66.3 percent” (Bureau of Labor Statistics, United States Department of Labor, 2020). [Appendix A Bureau of Labor Statistics, United States Department of Labor, Highlights from the 2019 Data](#). According to a United Kingdom Briefing Paper, “the unemployment rate for disabled people was 6.5% in April-June 2020. This compared to an unemployment rate of 3.5% for who are not disabled” (Commons Library Briefing, 2020). [Appendix B United Kingdom Key Labour Market Statistics by Disability Status, 2020](#).

Discussion

Frank Gilbreth and Dr. Lillian Gilbreth

Frank Gilbreth, an engineer, “was concerned with the technical aspects of worker efficiency; Dr. Lillian Gilbreth, a psychologist, was concerned with the human aspects of time” (SDSC.edu, n.d.) Their contemporary partnering of engineering and psychology would lay the groundwork for modern day Industrial Psychology. “As a team, the Gilbreths are probably best known for their studies of motion, the results of which enhanced worker efficiency and, hence, productivity” (Wood & Wood, 2003, p.171). Their book titled, “Motion Study”, published in 1911, was unique for its time in that it applied Dr. Lillian Gilbreth’s influence of psychology to the workplace, identifying the importance of “the human factor and its quality, in addition to motion, tools, equipment, and surrounding” as all essential “to bringing a system to work” (Worldsupporter, n.d.).

When Frank Gilbreth recognized that starting and stopping the stopwatch, used to study the motions of workers, was inefficient; they developed a process using the relatively new “motion picture film to quantify the number of motions involved in a specific work task and the time required to carry it out” (Bachmann, 2018). From that data and images, they were able to create a model, based on a unit of measure called the ‘therblig’ that is still in use today, “to calibrate and adjust basic human motion for greater efficiency and less physical and mental stress” (Bachmann, 2018). The results and publications thereof were applied in the workplace to “help employers understand how to modify environments and workflows to accommodate the worker’s physical limitations” (Bachmann, 2018).

Influenced by Frank Gilbreth’s tour of Europe during World War I, the Gilbreths became interested in another area of research on disabled workers, the wounded soldiers. As soldiers returned from World War I, Frank and Dr. Lillian Gilbreth “became proponents of workplace solutions for those with disabilities” (Bachmann, 2018). Subsequently, the United States Army “used their motion studies of the disabled to rehabilitate World War II amputees” (Wood & Wood, Eds, 2003, p. 172). Ultimately, the Gilbreths influenced the passage of laws, including the American with Disabilities Act (ADA). Their research also contributed to the expansion of the options for Occupational Rehabilitation and the development of the study of Ergonomics. [Appendix C Data on United States Disabled Veterans Unemployment Rates](#)

First and foremost, the Gilbreths recognized that “jobs and technology should be developed for people, and not vice versa” (Wood & Wood, 2003, p. 176). In their book, “Motion Study for the Handicapped”, Frank Gilbreth and Dr. Lillian Gilbreth proposed “discovering the method of least waste, that is, the method of doing the work best fitted to become the standard method” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 32). Then, use the information to (1) adapt the method to the worker; (2) if the worker has no strong preference or aptitude for any particular kind of work, assign the worker to an appropriate type of work; and (3) suggest inventions and changes that will make work and worker a better fit. Their desire was to emphasize the last point: the suggestion of automatic invention (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 33).

In order to stimulate invention, the Gilbreths suggested collecting (1) information on how individual people with disabilities have succeeded; (2) all data on revisions to equipment for people with disabilities; and (3) “all data on the elimination of fatigue, and the provision of rest for quickest recovery from necessary fatigue” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920,

p. 37). Accordingly, they also recognized the relevance of changes that would have to be made in labor relations and in job classifications (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p.118).

During their research, they were “astounded to learn” that a disabled person “thinking for the first time in terms of motions, and how that person can make those motions more efficient; becomes actually more interested in life when he realizes the possibilities of motion economy and of utilization of motion possibilities” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 38). With that, they realized that there were not only mechanical issues to be resolved, “but also psychological” issues, as well (p. 39).

After Frank Gilbreth’s death in 1924, Dr. Lillian Gilbreth assumed the position of president for their consulting company and continued to develop their research. At first shunned by former clients and industry, Dr. Gilbreth persevered. In time, her talent and skills were requested by “all major office machine companies (e.g., typewriters), appliance companies (e.g., refrigerators), hospitals (e.g., surgeon’s and nurse’s tasks), and in sports (e.g., champion golfers)” to change the product designs to accommodate the needs of people (Wood & Wood, 2003, p. 176). Moreover, Dr. Gilbreth’s diversity in the field of research supported the generalizability of her “theories, methods, and analysis” (Wood & Wood, 2003, p. 176).

The Virtual (Offsite) Office

According to Liz Johnson, managing director and cofounder, Steve Carter, of The Ability People, a United-Kingdom-based social enterprise, the employment level for people with disabilities has remained low due to “a lack of understanding, education, and exposure that results in people making comfortable hiring choices and overlooking talent pools of difference” (Stengel, 2020). Yet, research indicates that inclusion and diversity “improves financial performance, sharpens problem-solving abilities, and enhances creativity and motion” (Stengel, 2020) (Zeller, 2011).

Johnson and Carter propose “that normalizing work from home opens the door to more people with disabilities to work” (Stengel, 2020). For instance, “remote work alleviates additional stressors”; such as, “getting dressed for work and commuting” (Stengel, 2020). Basically, technology can provide the ability to work from wherever; thus, circumventing the need for transportation to and accessibility in a “fixed workspace” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 56).

In their text “Motion Studies for the Handicapped”, Frank Gilbreth and Dr. Lillian Gilbreth emphasize that “it is the measurement that has resulted in better placement, and in assigning each individual to that type of work for which he will become best fitted, and that he finds interesting” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 71). However, measuring the productivity of the virtual workforce continues to be an evolving science; and a combined virtual and traditional workforce presents additional challenges. In 1997, “Ralph Westfall proposed a group of hypotheses concerning telework productivity suggesting that there were many pitfalls in measurements. He speculated that reported gains could be biased by factors such as selection of better workers for telework than for ‘normal’ work, unreliability of self-reported productivity gains, inability to separate improvements due to telework from overall management improvements, additional costs for telework not included in analyses, and difficulty in gauging returns that computers gain from telework as more employees participate” (Ruth & Chaudhry, 2008, p. 89) (Zeller, 2018, Fall).

Though “performance management, if done effectively, can help avoid discrimination”; “Title 1 of the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) and Section 501 of the Rehabilitation Act, which prohibit employment discrimination against qualified individuals with disabilities, generally do not impinge on the right of employers to define jobs and to evaluate their employees according to consistently applied standards governing performance and conduct” (U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission, 2008). From a human resource viewpoint, performance appraisal systems should be based on the merit of the work; thereby, recognizing all employees ready for “higher levels of responsibilities” (Southwest ADA Center, n.d.) (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 60). Moreover, the “reasonable accommodation” clause in the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) means “equal opportunity, not merely equal treatment” (Pati & Bailey, 1995, p. 58). In this case, up-to-date job descriptions can help to ascertain that all applicants, including persons with disabilities, have the “requisite skills, educational background, and experience to perform the essential functions” (Dessler, 2004, p. 130) (Zeller, 2011).

Overall, the virtual workplace requires a transition from viewable management to management that is outcome or results-based (Cascio, 2000, p. 81)(Zeller, 2018, Spring). “Shirley Davis-Sheppard, the Society for Human Resources Management’s vice-president of Global Diversity & Inclusion” advises that “employees shouldn’t have to tell the organization the reason for wanting to work virtually.” In fact, “[SHRM’s Global Diversity & Inclusion division] “advocates that companies should be managing by results, not ‘butts in seats’.” Ms. Davis-Sheppard, “who is also the co-leader of the Society for Human Resources Management’s Workplace Flexibility initiative and holds a doctorate in business and organization management”, goes on to say “That’s what inclusion is all about...[organizations] are not going to be able to engage and retain great talent without having flexibility. “ Furthermore, Davis-Sheppard advises that “this is not just about telecommuting. It’s about compressed workweeks, part-time job options, flexible schedules and job sharing.” Appendix D: The Positive Influence of a Diverse Workforce on Strategy Execution

Summary and Recommendations for Future Research

The global data indicates that there hasn’t been a significant change in the unemployment rate for persons with disabilities. The question remains as to whether the ‘stickiness’ in the relatively unchanged data is an indication of a pervasive practice of inequality in the workplace. Appendix E United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Disability.

The Gilbreths suggested collecting (1) information on how individual people with disabilities have succeeded; (2) all data on revisions to equipment for people with disabilities; and (3) “all data on the elimination of fatigue, and the provision of rest for quickest recovery from necessary fatigue” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 37). Accordingly, they also recognized the relevance of changes that would have to be made in labor relations and in job classifications (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p.118).

Recommendations for future research include methodology, employment data analysis, and human resource practices and policies.

Methodology

Richard Hyman “asserts that to discover some statistical association between variables does not entail either the development or testing of theory, and by implication, he suggests that qualitative research focused on processes and meaning would prove more illuminating. Societal phenomena must be analyzed in terms of actually existing structures and causal mechanisms that are not necessarily directly observable (and hence quantifiable)—a conviction which is, of course, a major challenge to the principles of empiricism and quantification” (Frege, Kelly, & McGovern, 2011, p. 216)

The Gilbreths were able to obtain “cooperation from industrial workers who eagerly embraced the opportunity to make their experience of use to others”; thereby, allowing the analysis of existing structures and causal mechanisms (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 22). Hence, they found that “many workers can be best provided for by some change that will adapt the work to the man”; e.g. “rearranging the surroundings, equipment, and tools; modifications of machinery; and / or changing the method by which the work is done” (p. 27). Currently though, “relatively few major steps have been taken to break theoretical and empirical ground to orient job design research towards fresh topics and phenomena”; including the orientation of job design to the virtual work environments (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 146) (Zeller, 2017).

Employment Data Analysis

The Brookings Institute, “a nonprofit public policy organization dedicated to helping solve problems facing society,” report that “only 40% of adults in the United States with disabilities in their prime working years (ages 25-54) have a job, compared to 79% of all prime age adults” (Stengel, 2020). In the United Kingdom, the unemployment rate for disabled people is “28.1 percentage points lower than that of people who are not disabled. The difference is often referred to as the disability employment gap” (House of Commons Briefing Paper, 2020, p. 4).

As for the disability employment gap, Frank Gilbreth and Dr. Lillian Gilbreth proposed that it is the duty of an organization “to take up the industrial end of the problem, to investigate existing conditions in the industries, to discover where the opportunities for employment lie, and to readjust industrial practice” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p 110).

Human Resource Practices and Policies

The human resource professional, working with diversity initiatives, can perform a “critical role in minimizing workplace discrimination for people with disabilities”; thereby, helping to create a culture in which professional and personal growth and development can be fulfilled (Southwest ADA Center, n.d.) (Zeller, 2011). For instance, in the ever-changing role of new technologies, initiatives can be developed to continually reassess job descriptions and performance appraisals (Inc., n.d.) (Zeller, 2019 Summer). The continual updates to job descriptions can help to ascertain that all applicants, including persons with disabilities, have the “requisite skills, educational background, and experience to perform the essential functions” (Dessler, 2004, p. 130) (Zeller, 2011). Then, to work toward creating a culture in which professional and personal growth and development can be fulfilled, “see that available information is placed where it can do the most good” (Gilbreth & Gilbreth, 1920, p. 38).

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Appendix A: Bureau of Labor Statistics, United States Department of Labor, Highlights from the 2019 Data

- Half of all persons with a disability were age 65 and over, about three times larger than the share of those with no disability.
- Across all age groups, the employment-population ratios were much lower for persons with a disability than for those with no disability.
- Across all educational attainment groups, unemployment rates for persons with a disability were higher than those for persons without a disability.
- In 2019, 32 percent of workers with a disability were employed part time, compared with 17 percent for those with no disability.
- Employed persons with a disability were more likely to be self-employed than those with no disability.

Appendix B: United Kingdom Key Labour Market Statistics by Disability Status, 2020

Appendix C Data on United States Disabled Veterans Unemployment Rates

From <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/vets/latest-numbers>

Employment Situation of Veterans – 2019

In 2019, the veteran unemployment rate was **3.1%** (the lowest in 19 years). [Read the full report.](#)

Some highlights from the 2019 report include:

- The unemployment rate for male veterans declined to 3.0 percent in 2019, and the rate for female veterans (3.7 percent) changed little over the year.
- Among the 284,000 unemployed veterans in 2019, 56 percent were ages 25 to 54, 39 percent were age 55 and over, and 5 were ages 18 to 24.
- Veterans with a service-connected disability had an unemployment rate of 4.8 percent in August 2019, not statistically different from the rate for veterans with no disability.
- In August 2019, 31 percent of employed veterans with a service-connected disability worked in the public sector, compared with 17 percent of veterans with no disability and 13 percent of nonveterans.
- In 2019, the unemployment rate of veterans varied across the country, ranging from 0.9 percent in Maryland to 6.1 percent in Montana.

Appendix D: The Positive Influence of a Diverse Workforce on Strategy Execution

“The business case for diversity and inclusion is intrinsically linked to a *company’s innovation strategy*. Multiple and varied voices have a wide range of experiences, and this can help generate new ideas about products and practices” (Forbes | Insights, 2011, p. 5).

Forbes | Insight (2011, July). Global diversity and inclusion fostering innovation through a diverse workforce. *Forbes | Insights*. Retrieved http://images.forbes.com/forbesinsights/StudyPDFs/Innovation_Through_Diversity.pdf

Appendix E: United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs Disability.

See <https://www.un.org/disabilities/documents/toolaction/employmentfs.pdf>

Excerpt:

Data on persons with disabilities are hard to come by in almost every country. Specific data on their employment situation are even harder to find. Yet persons with disabilities face the same predicament everywhere. These data (see link to pdf file above), culled from the media and from reports, provide an anecdotal picture of the current situation.

Global

In developing countries, 80% to 90% of persons with disabilities of working age are unemployed, whereas in industrialized countries the figure is between 50% and 70%. 'Disabled still face hurdles in the job market', The Washington Times, 5 December 2005

In most developed countries the official unemployment rate for persons with disabilities of working age is at least twice that for those who have no disability. Employer's Forum on Disability, www.employers-forum.co.uk/www/guests/info/csr/disability-online

